

STUDIES ON CLERODIN. THE ACTIVE PRINCIPLE OF *CLERODENDRON INFORTUNATUM*. PART I

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Clerodin, the active principle of the leaves of *clerodendron infortunatum* has been investigated. By following a modified method it has been obtained in an increased yield and reinvestigation of the active principle confirms its formula to be $C_{28}H_{40}O_4$ instead of $C_{33}H_{48}O_4$, as reported by Banerjee.

Banerjee (this *Journal*, 1937, 14, 51) first isolated clerodin, a colorless, crystalline active principle (m.p. $161-62^\circ$, $[\alpha]_D^{25} = +45.4$) from the leaves of *Clerodendron infortunatum* in 0.12% yield, to which he assigned the formula $C_{33}H_{48}O_4$. By adopting a modified method of isolation and using dried leaves just after rains we have, however, been able to increase its yield considerably (0.75%) and the melting point of clerodin by repeated recrystallisation could be raised to $164-65^\circ$. On the basis of his formula Banerjee (*Trans. Bose Res. Inst.*, 1935-1936, 11, 71) accounted one of the oxygen atoms as present in an alcoholic hydroxyl group, since by using rather drastic conditions he claimed to have prepared a crystalline monoacetyl derivative, m.p. 110° , which in spite of our repeated attempts to reproduce could only be obtained as an intractable product. Moreover, though he reported to have obtained (*Trans. Bose Res. Inst.*, 1936-1937, 12, 75) dihydroclerodin (m.p. 115°) by reduction with H-Pt or Zn-acetic acid and an aromatic monobasic acid ($C_{13}H_{16}O_4$, m.p. 265°) by oxidation with $KMnO_4$ -acetone or with CrO_3 , we were unable to confirm his views as repeated attempts to reproduce his results of reduction and oxidation invariably gave rise to either gummy products or amorphous mass which could not be crystallised. From the studies of a large number of reduction (e.g. with Pd-C/H, Adams PtO_2 -catalyst, Zn-acetic acid) and oxidation (e.g. with alkaline permanganate, acid permanganate, dichromate and sulphuric acid, chromic acid in acetic acid in cold as well as hot) experiments, even under varying conditions, we were led to conclude that degradation of clerodin by the usual oxidising and reducing agents appeared difficult to control as only inconsistent results were obtained which could not be reproduced.

Having failed to confirm the experimental results of Banerjee (*loc. cit.*) we decided to re-examine the issue from the very beginning. Contrary to his claims, a series of molecular weight determinations both by cryoscopic and Rast camphor methods as well as the analyses of clerodin and its derivatives appeared to indicate its formula as $C_{28}H_{40}O_4$. The acetylation of clerodin has, however, been achieved under comparatively mild experimental conditions and the analytical results of the crystalline acetyl derivative (m.p. 205°) are in close agreement with the possibility of its being a tetra-acetate of clerodin, a fact indicating the presence of four hydroxyl groups in clerodin, which being non-phenolic in character, presumably must be alcoholic.

On the basis of his formula Banerjee (*loc. cit.*) accounted the three oxygen atoms in clerodin as one for the alcoholic hydroxyl and other two in one O-acetyl group

(-O.CO.CH₃), the presence of the latter he indicated only by its estimation without giving, whatsoever, any confirmatory evidence to substantiate the presence of such an ester group in the clerodin molecule. In view of the striking difference between our proposed formula and the one assigned by him for clerodin, we next decided to establish the presence of a O.CO.CH₃ group in the molecule. The isolation of acetic acid by acid hydrolysis and its identification as acetanilide, together with the fact that deacetylation of clerodin by mild alkaline hydrolysis followed by reacylation of desacetylclerodin to yield acetylclerodin, identical with the tetra-acetate obtained directly from clerodin by acetylation, as diagrammatically shown below, definitely prove the existence of the *O*-acetyl group which, when estimated, gave the values for one such group in the molecule, a result in keeping with the assumption that clerodin is represented by the formula C₂₆H₄₀O₈.

Thus, out of the eight oxygen atoms in clerodin two are accounted in the ester group (O.CO.CH₃), four in the alcoholic hydroxyl groups and the remaining two, in the absence of any alkoxy or carbonyl group, appear to be present in ether linkages.

The presence of such a considerable number of alcoholic hydroxyl groups in clerodin suggested the possibility of its being a glycoside, but when the aqueous solution after hydrolysis of clerodin either with aqueous-alcoholic HCl or sulphuric acid was examined, it was found difficult to form any definite conclusion, because the neutralised aqueous solution after hydrolysis failed to reduce Fehling's solution readily though after prolonged heating the solution deposited red cuprous oxide on long standing and with Tollen's reagent the hydrolytic aqueous solution gave once a silver mirror which could not be reproduced except that on repeating the experiment only a little black deposit of silver was obtained. The rather slow and inconclusive reducing property of the hydrolytic solution appears to be due to the presence of impurities in the alcohol, the use of which is necessary to keep clerodin in solution during hydrolysis, since an aqueous-alcoholic Fehling's solution alone is slowly reduced on prolonged heating. The traces of the yellow product, obtained by the interaction of the hydrolytic solution with phenylhydrazine acetate, being largely contaminated with oily impurities, could not be purified to permit its characterisation.

A search in the literature indicated that clerodin, C₂₆H₄₀O₈, having such a high molecular weight with its characteristic property of producing copious froth during acid hydrolysis might belong to the steroid class of compounds and as such when clerodin itself or the product, obtained by acid hydrolysis as a low melting solid, was subjected to the colour reactions of a sterol, the results were found to agree with our anticipation. It gave red coloration in Libermann-Burchard test, purple in Salkowski's test, deep red in Tschugajeff test and no coloration in Rosenheims test, the last

reaction indicating the absence of a system containing or potentially containing a conjugated system of carbon atoms. Since the pyridine solution of clerodin failed to respond to Legal's test it could not belong to the class of cardiac poisons having a $\beta\gamma$ -unsaturated lactone ring.

Thus, for the complete elucidation of the structure of clerodin further investigation, which is necessary, is awaiting the isolation of a substantial quantity of the natural product.

EXPERIMENTAL

Isolation.—Four batches of the dried powdered leaves of *C. infortunatum* (500 g. each) was exhaustively extracted in a soxhlet with petroleum ether (b. p. 60°-80°). Distillation of the petroleum ether from the extract left a thick mass of dark green coloured needles which were repeatedly extracted with cold alcohol (96%, 200 c.c. $\times$ 10), the combined alcoholic solution after concentrating to a small bulk (200 c.c.) on standing almost solidified to a thick paste of long needles which were filtered off from the dark mother-liquor (L) and washed with a little cold dilute alcohol. For purification, the crystals were dissolved in hot alcohol (96%, 200 c.c.) and the solution diluted with a large volume of water when yellow needles separated out which were collected by filtration. Repetition of the process of dissolving in alcohol and precipitation with water gradually removed the colouring matter yielding almost colorless needles (P) which were set aside for further purification.

A further quantity of clerodin was obtained from the dark mother-liquor (L) which after concentration to a thick syrup, when poured into a large volume of cold water, precipitated a yellow crystalline mass contaminated with tarry matter which was filtered through a plug of cotton. The residue was repeatedly extracted with boiling water, the extracts filtered hot through cotton which retained most of the tarry matter and the turbid aqueous filtrate, on cooling, deposited almost pure long needles (Q) which were filtered off.

The crystalline residues (P & Q) were combined, dissolved in the minimum quantity of hot alcohol and water added just to turbidity; on standing, the solution deposited long silky needles of clerodin which were recrystallised several times from dilute ethyl alcohol and finally from methyl alcohol in rosettes of slender glistening needles, m.p. 164-65° (Banerjee, *loc cit.* records m.p. 161-62°), yield 15 g. (0.75%).

[Found M. W. (cryoscopic) in benzene: 491, 498; (Rast) 472, 492, 504, 540. Calc. for $C_{28}H_{46}O_8$: M.W., 504 (cf. Banerjee records M.W. 207, 212, 217, 222)]. (Found: C, 66.68; 66.51 H, 7.87, 7.75. $C_{28}H_{46}O_8$ requires C, 66.46; H, 7.93 per cent) (cf. Banerjee, $C_{13}H_{18}O_3$ requires C, 70.27; H, 8.1%). (Found: acetyl, 8.37. Calc. for one acetyl: $C_{28}H_{46}O_8$ requires 8.5 per cent).

Clerodin is almost insoluble in water, highly soluble in ethyl alcohol, methyl alcohol, acetone and the other usual organic solvents. Its solution is neutral to litmus. It is insoluble in cold and hot aqueous caustic soda, though in alcoholic caustic soda it dissolves at room temperature imparting yellow colour to the solution, but is not reprecipitated on acidification. It neither reduces Tollen's reagent nor Fehling's solution and its alcoholic solution does not give any characteristic colour with ferric chloride. Though it rapidly decolorises bromine in carbon tetrachloride, it slowly

discharges the colour of permanganate in acetone solution. It dissolves in cold concentrated sulphuric acid with intense red coloration and in cold concentrated HCl with no coloration from which it is not precipitated by dilution with a large volume of water. It does not react with 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazine but readily responds to the hydroxamate test for an ester.

Acetylation of Clerodin.—A mixture of clerodin (0.7 g.), freshly fused powdered sodium acetate (1.5 g.) and freshly distilled acetic anhydride (5 c.c.) was heated on the water-bath for two hours, cooled, poured into ice-water with stirring and allowed to stand for 24 hours. The solid after filtration was thoroughly washed with water and dissolved in the minimum amount of warm methyl alcohol and the solution treated with water until a faint turbidity appeared. On being kept, this solution deposited the acetate in prismatic needles, m.p. 198° - 203° which were finally recrystallised from methyl alcohol in colorless prismatic needles or in rectangular prisms, m.p. 205° . (Found: C, 64.43, 64.31; H, 7.44, 7.39. $C_{36}H_{48}O_{12}$ requires C, 64.28; H, 7.14 per cent).

Attempts to prepare the acetyl derivative, according to the method of Banerjee (*loc. cit.*) by using acetyl chloride, gave a white amorphous solid which could not be induced to crystallise.

Acid-hydrolysis of Clerodin with 50% H_2SO_4 .—A mixture of clerodin (1 g.) and sulphuric acid (50%, 100 c.c.) was refluxed over a small flame for half an hour, when a brown precipitate which separated out in the beginning gradually became darker and the solution produced a vigorous froth during the course of boiling. The brown reaction mixture after cooling was very carefully transferred to a distilling flask to overcome the difficulty of vigorous frothing and about 100 c.c. of the distillate was slowly collected through an efficient condenser, fresh water being frequently added during distillation from the dropping funnel fitted to the top of the distilling flask to keep the volume of the reaction mixture almost constant. The distillate, which was strongly acidic, was treated with a drop of phenolphthalein and next exactly neutralised with the dropwise addition of an alcoholic solution of caustic soda, the neutral solution slowly evaporated to dryness on the water-bath until a solid residue was obtained. The solid (0.5 g.) which responded to the qualitative tests for an acetate, viz. (a) red coloration with ferric chloride, (b) vinegar smell with warm dilute sulphuric acid and (c) cacodyl oxide reaction, was mixed with a little freshly distilled aniline (1 g.) and HCl (conc., 0.5 c.c.). After heating the mixture for 45 minutes under reflux it was cooled, mixed with alcohol (5 c.c.), again boiled and the alcoholic extract poured into hot water (40 c.c.). The solution on evaporation to dryness left a residue which was extracted with ether, the ether evaporated when an oily residue was left behind. This oily product was extracted with a small quantity of hot water, the aqueous solution concentrated, cooled and on standing it immediately deposited glistening crystals, which on recrystallisation from a little very dilute alcohol, yielded the pure product, m.p. 112° , identical in every way with an authentic specimen of acetanilide, m.p. and mixed m.p. 112 - 14° .

Hydrolysis of Clerodin with Aqueous-alcoholic HCl.—A solution of clerodin (0.4 g.) in alcohol (96%, 20 c.c.) was treated with dilute HCl (2N, 0.3 c.c.) and the

solution refluxed for 3 hours. After distilling off the alcohol, the syrupy residue was treated with water and on being allowed to stand overnight, the residue solidified. The aqueous solution which was decanted off, reduced hot Fehling's solution rather slowly, depositing red cuprous oxide on standing and also Tollen's reagent giving a silver mirror. Interaction of the aqueous solution with a dilute solution of phenylhydrazine acetate on the water-bath gave traces of a yellow product which being largely contaminated with oily impurities could not be purified. Similar results were obtained with aqueous-alcoholic sulphuric acid. The solid residue responded to the tests of a sterol.

Alkaline Hydrolysis of Clerodin by KOH—aq. MeOH.—Clerodin (0.5 g.), dissolved in methyl alcohol (10 c.c.), was mixed with an aqueous solution of caustic potash (0.8 g. in 80 c.c. water) when clerodin immediately precipitated out from the solution. An additional quantity (30 c.c.) of methyl alcohol was added and warmed to obtain a clear solution which when refluxed on the water-bath for 1 hour deposited gradually a white shining sandy solid. After cooling it was filtered off, washed with water to remove the alkali, followed by methyl alcohol to remove any unchanged clerodin and recrystallised from a large volume of hot chloroform in glistening rectangular prisms, m.p. 242-43° with previous sintering at 240°, yield 0.35 g. (Found : C, 67.46, 67.59 ; H, 8.47, 8.43. $C_{26}H_{38}O_7$, requires C, 67.53 ; H, 8.2 per cent).

This compound is soluble in a large volume of hot chloroform and glacial acetic acid, and unlike clerodin, insoluble in methanol, ethyl alcohol and in most of the common organic solvents. Concentrated sulphuric acid imparts red colour to the crystals and on warming, the mixture is charred ; with concentrated hydrochloric acid no change is observed and on heating the solution becomes yellow, most of the compound remaining undissolved. An alcoholic suspension gives no characteristic coloration with ferric chloride and the substance is also insoluble in alkalis. The substance remains unchanged with cold aqueous permanganate but on heating the colour of the permanganate is discharged. A solution of the compound in chloroform, when treated with bromine in carbon tetrachloride does not decolorise it.

The above deacetylated product (0.25 g.) was mixed with fused sodium acetate (1 g.) and acetic anhydride (5 c.c.) and heated on the water-bath for 2 hours. After cooling, the reaction mixture was poured into ice-water when a semi-crystalline solid separated out, which was filtered, washed with water and on recrystallisation from methyl alcohol yielded the pure product, m.p. 204°-205°, undepressed on admixture with the synthetical specimen of acetylclerodin, m.p. 205°.

Oxidation Experiments : (a) *With solid $KMnO_4$ in Acetone solution.*—A solution of clerodin (0.5 g.) in acetone (10 c.c.) was gradually treated with finely powdered $KMnO_4$ (0.4 g.) in portions during 3 hours and left overnight. The diluted reaction mixture after clarifying with SO_2 was extracted with ether and the oily residue left after evaporation of the ether dissolved partially in aqueous bicarbonate with effervescence ; the filtered bicarbonate solution on acidification gave a gummy product which could not be crystallised. The neutral insoluble portion was also found intractable (cf. Banerjee, *loc. cit.*, a crystalline acid, m.p. 265° by this method).

(b) *With Aqueous $KMnO_4$ in Acetone solution.*—Clerodin (2.5 g.) in acetone (100 c.c.) was treated with vigorous shaking in portions with an aqueous solution of permanganate (5%, 100 c.c.) at 20°. After 72 hours the diluted reaction mixture was clarified with SO_2 and the acetone distilled off. The aqueous solution was extracted with ether and on evaporation of the ether a colorless, glass-like transparent syrup was left which could not be crystallised.

The aqueous solution after ether extraction was acidified and again extracted with ether, the extract washed, dried and ether removed when a few needles contaminated with oil were obtained. Once crystallised from ethyl acetate it melted at 235°. The quantity being very small, further purification could not be undertaken. The product is insoluble in aqueous bicarbonate and caustic soda.

Reaction with 3:5-Dinitrobenzoyl Chloride.—(a). A solution of clerodin (0.2 g.) and 3:5-dinitrobenzoyl chloride (0.2 g.) in anhydrous benzene (2 c.c.) was treated with pyridine (1 c.c.) and heated just to boiling. After allowing the reaction mixture to stand at the room temperature for 48 hours, it was mixed with ether, the ethereal solution washed with dilute HCl, dilute caustic soda and a large volume of water in succession, and the ether removed when an oily residue was left behind. On crystallisation from methyl alcohol it was found to be unchanged clerodin, m.p. 167°.

(b) A mixture of clerodin (0.2 g.), 3:5-dinitrobenzoyl chloride (0.2 g.), dry benzene (2 c.c.) and pyridine (1 c.c.) was refluxed for 2 hours. The cooled red mixture was extracted with ether and on working up the ethereal layer in the way described previously, a red gummy product was obtained. It was taken up in a little methanol and on being set aside for slow evaporation deposited colorless crystals contaminated with red sticky matter, during the course of a few days. The colorless crystals were picked up and on recrystallisation from methyl alcohol gave colorless prisms, m.p. 92°-93° with previous sintering at 88°. Attempts to repeat this experiment to get this crystalline substance in sufficient quantity for further purification and analysis, however, failed as the red sticky matter with which it invariably remained contaminated could not be removed.

All micro-analyses and micro-determinations were carried out in U. K.